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D9.2 Final Report on Transnational Access 2

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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
TA	Transnational Access
RIL	Research Infrastructure Leader
CA	Contract Agreement
BA	Bilateral Agreement

Executive summary

This executive summary presents the global overview of the transnational access (TA) activities conducted in Work Package 9 (WP9) TA2 - TA to Living Lab (LL) infrastructures for transitional care as part of the VITALISE project. This final comprehensive report offers an in-depth review of the transnational access activities conducted across four participating research infrastructures. The final reports completed by the visiting research teams could be provided upon request to the following e-mail: vitalise-helpdesk@googlegroups.com.

The document highlights the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art LL infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation and advance knowledge in the field of Transitional Care.

The report reflects on the entire span of the project providing an analysis of all TA activities and the overall evaluation results, highlighting the several research projects conducted, outcomes achieved, and notable advancements or discoveries. This comprehensive overview underlines the TA program's vital role in fulfilling the VITALISE project's primary objectives and demonstrates the tangible impact of these collaborative efforts, underscore the project's enduring commitment to exploring new research avenues and maximizing the potential of Living Lab infrastructures.

As the final comprehensive report, this document is a culmination of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP9's TA2. It showcases the project's success in fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of transitional care. Serving as an essential resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, this report provides critical insights into the project's overall outcomes and its lasting impact in the field.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP9

Work Package 9 (WP9) is focused on the centralized and coordinated design and implementation of Transnational Access for Infrastructures related with the domain of transitional care. The term “Transnational Access” (TA) refers to the usage of VITALISE infrastructures by researchers located in countries other than where the accessed infrastructure is located.

WP9 encompasses four research infrastructures: 1) AUTH Health care transition Living Lab, 2) INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room, 3) Thomas More experience lab and 4) UPM-LifeSTech - The Smart House Living Lab.

The support offered during TA visits includes, but is not limited to, logistics management, provision of working space, scientific support by Living Lab researchers for stakeholder management, assistance in preparing and submitting ethical applications, conducting experiments, and technical support for maintenance or resolving technology issues, if necessary.

The TA procedure and manual is handled in WP11 NA4 - Calls for ideas and proposals, experiment selection. Efforts for outreach to new users are described in WP13, utilizing the project website and existing communication channels of ENoLL, EIT Health LL, and Forum LLSA. Capacity-building activities in WP4 and the calls in WP11 facilitate outreach and selection of approved proposals.

1.2 Purpose of the document

The purpose of the D9.2 "Final Report on Transnational Access 2" is to summarize the activities conducted under the VITALISE project's Work Package 9 TA2 - TA to Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care. The report describes the completed transnational access activities across four research infrastructures. It details the research conducted, the outcomes, and significant findings from the completed activities.

As a definitive summary of WP9's TA2 efforts, this report is a testament to the progress achieved in interdisciplinary research and as a valuable tool for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, offering deep insights into the Transnational Access Program impact and the potential directions for future research in the field of everyday living.

The report is linked to the activities and information collected in the Transactional Accesses of WP8 and WP10, having the same structure as D8.2 "Final Report on Transnational Access 1" and D10.2 "Final Report on Transnational Access 3". The final reports completed by the visiting research teams could be provided upon request to the following e-mail: vitalise-helpdesk@googlegroups.com.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1 (Introduction)** provides a description of Work Package 9 (WP9), outlines the purpose of the document, and presents the structure of the report.
- **Section 2 (Transnational Access Projects)** includes the overall evaluation results, as analyzed from the responses of visiting researchers to the “After TA evaluation questionnaires”. It also provides details for each Transnational Access (TA) project, presenting in the PROJECT SUMMARY the background, set objectives, adopted research methodologies and the principal results achieved. The CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK of this section not only reflects on the conclusions drawn from each TA project, but also reflects on the immediate aftermath of the TA and ventures into potential future collaborations and researcher evaluations. Then the TA EVALUATION offers insights of the researchers’ evaluation and feedback and present the Living Lab personnel dedicated efforts including hours spent.

- **Section 3 (Discussion)** offers an overview of the WP9 TA results, as well as a reflective analysis including overall LL experience of the Living Labs in relation to the TAs, distilling lessons learnt and experience gained throughout the process, as well as insightful information about the services utilized during the TA research studies.
- **Section 4 (Conclusion)** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Transnational Access projects

This section initially presents the overall evaluation results as analyzed from the responses of visiting researchers to the “After TA evaluation questionnaire” answers of the Transnational Access to the Transitional Care Infrastructures.

In addition, this section offers an insightful description of all the TA projects that have been performed in each of the WP9 Living Lab infrastructures. It also contains the information in case of cancellation or amendment of the TA.

2.1 Overall evaluation results

The evaluation of the visiting researchers' experience from the TA to the Transitional Care Infrastructures presented below, is based on their feedback provided through the “After-TA evaluation questionnaire” (see ANNEX), which they were required to complete individually, upon concluding their research studies. These questionnaires, developed by VITALISE partners on the EUSurvey platform prior to the TA Open Calls, were distributed to participating researchers via a provided link for completion. We received a total of 19 responses in the “After-TA evaluation questionnaire” from the 22 participants in the TA to the Transitional Care Infrastructures.

The analysis of the responses shows an overall positive experience. All 19 responders answered 8 or above to the first question (“How likely are you to recommend Transnational Access to your colleagues or other researchers (0 not at all – 10 very likely)”). We also calculated the Net Promoter Score (NPS), asking respondents to rate the likelihood of recommending the TA experience to colleagues. The NPS is calculated by subtracting the Detractors from the Promoters. Promoters are considered those who answered above or equal to 9, Passives are those that answered from 7 to 8 and Detractors are those who answered below or equal to 6. Eighteen (18) out of nineteen (19) responders, approximately 95% (94.7%.) were promoters and there were zero (0) detractors. This results in an NPS equal to 95 (Figure 1).

The participants were also asked to rate how well their expectations were met, on a 5-point Likert scale (much higher, higher, as expected, lower, much lower). The total percentage of expectations met is 94.7% (17 out of 19) that reflects the responders who answered "much higher", "higher" or "as expected". More precisely, one (1) participant stated that the output was "as expected", fifteen (15) participants responded that they experienced a higher output and two (2) participants responded that they experienced a much higher output.

In terms of quality, the analysis of the services provided shows that the rating is mostly high, with very few neutral and low responses in each category. The questions that were analysed were those of section 6: “Please rate the following services provided by the hosting Living Lab in terms of quality”. The services were rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from very low to very high, also providing the NA option. The services rated were the following:

1. Methodological support and guidance,
2. Physical infrastructure,
3. Expertise/support with end users,
4. Understanding of end-user needs and problems
5. Selection/recruitment of research participants

Each question of section 6 represented one service. The percentage of “very high” and “high” answers was the most common, with very few “low” and “neutral” answers and none “very low” answers. The Overall Satisfaction percentage was based on the answers to all the questions that were related to the quality of services. More specifically, we counted all the instances of High and Very High answers to all 5 questions related to the quality of services (95 answers in total). Eighty-seven (87) out of ninety-five (95) responses (91.5%) declared a positive attitude (high or very high satisfaction) for the services provided.

The following dashboard (Figure 1) contains the data visualizations of the analysis conducted on the questionnaires in terms of quality and satisfaction of the TA visiting researchers.

Figure 1 Quality of services provided by the TA LL infrastructures

Further analysis of the answers to the fourth (“What did you appreciate most about the Transnational Access?”) and seventh (“7.B What do you think are key strengths in terms of expertise/coaching/etc. of the visited research infrastructure from the perspective of your research or study?”) open questions, led to the discovery of the TA key strengths, as reported by the researchers. The responses were analysed using qualitative content analysis. Coding the main points of each answer and grouping them based on common elements, we eventually concluded in the following three (3) categories that represent the TA key strengths.

1. Collaborative and Supportive Environment
2. Access to Resources and Infrastructure
3. Multidisciplinary Collaboration

Accordingly, following the same method described above, we analysed the answers to the fifth (“Do you have any suggestions for improvement concerning the Transnational Access?”) and seventh (“7C. What weaknesses in the visited research infrastructure do you believe need to be addressed? These could include any aspect of the institution that hinders your research productivity”) open questions, resulting to the following two (2) TA suggestions for improvement:

1. Translation support
2. Facilitate the access to vulnerable groups

Additionally, the answers to open questions thirteen (“Is there any other service or product you anticipate needing in your future research?”) and fourteen (“Any additional comments you would like to share with us?”) complemented the strengths or the suggestions of the categories mentioned above.

2.2 Presentation of the TA research projects

This section offers an insightful description of all the TA projects that have been performed in each of the WP9 Living Lab infrastructures. For each TA research project, we have included a dedicated session for the following aspects:

- **PROJECT SUMMARY**

Background, set objectives, adopted research methodologies and principal results achieved

- **CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE OUTLOOK**

Reflects on the conclusions drawn from each TA project, and on the immediate aftermath of the TAs and ventures into potential future collaborations and researcher evaluations

- **TA EVALUATION**

Reflects on researchers' evaluation and feedback and present the LL personnel dedicated efforts including hours spent, extracted from the TA monitoring Excel spreadsheet, the Excel file where all the LLs were reporting the hours spent by both LL staff and researchers for the realization of each TA project separately. Regarding the LL personnel dedicated efforts, the total sum of hours spent by all the LL staff members supporting the execution of each TA project (both in person and remotely) was calculated. The total number of person days was calculated by counting and summing the total days where the indicated hours were above 0 for each LL staff member.

2.2.1 AUTH Health care transition Living Lab

AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab has completed a total of three (3) Transnational Access projects in the period from February 2023 to February 2024. A total of nine (9) researchers visited the AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab, four belonging to TA ID9 (instead of five who initially applied), three belonging to TA ID21 (instead of one who initially applied) and two to TA ID35. From the TA studies performed in this specific AUTH LL infrastructure, three abstracts were submitted to the Health & Wellbeing Living Lab Symposium in Brussels on the 20th of February, 2024 and one of them was selected to be pitched during the Symposium, entitled: "Empowering Unpaid Carers: An Industry-University Collaboration in Testing An AI-Powered Solution in the ThessAHALL".

Project	TA period	TA Services	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	Nº of researchers	Visit performed
Gold Health Care (ID9)	Feb 2023	<i>Living lab project planning and management, Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Panel management, Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping, Co-creation session, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support</i>	-	20	4	Yes
HESTIA (ID21)	Jan-Feb 2024	<i>Living lab project planning and management, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support, Expert opinion and advisory services, Panel management, Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation</i>	86	20	3	Yes

DSCS (ID35)	Sep-Oct 2023	<i>Living lab project planning and management, Capacity building, Panel management, Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping, Intake and matching, Expert opinion and advisory services, Co-creation session, Legal, regulation, and safety standard support</i>	4	34	2	Yes
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Table 1 AUTH Health Care Transition LL Projects – Current Status

“Gold Health Care” project – ID9

2.2.1.1.1 Project summary

Participant researchers: Fatjona Kamberi (lead applicant), Glodiana Sinanaj, Brunilda Subashi, Jerina Jaho - University of Vlore "Ismail Qemali"

The main purpose of the “Gold Health Care” project was to implement innovative approaches to healthcare tailored to vulnerable groups of older adults for better healthcare and aging. This was envisaged to be accomplished by creating a wide local knowledge framework, detailing health care barriers, facilitators and needs among vulnerable groups of older people through working in close collaboration with them and use the findings to generate evidence-based interventions and policies.

Within this context, in AUTH infrastructures the visiting research team aimed to conduct a first mapping and evaluation of the barriers, challenges, shortcomings but, also, the benefits of health care interventions targeting vulnerable groups of older people.

For the purposes of this TA, four researchers, Fatjona Kamberi (lead applicant), Glodiana Sinanaj, Brunilda Subashi and Jerina Jaho from the University of Vlore "Ismail Qemali" visited AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab in Thessaloniki, Greece. The visiting period for the four researchers was the week from the 20th till the 24th of February 2023. During this period, they were introduced to various technologies and resources available in the lab and they had the opportunity to conduct two co-creation sessions, one with health care professionals and one with a group of older adults.

Before the conduct of the co-creation sessions, the VITALISE research team along with the visiting researchers discussed the details of the sessions, how and where they will be held, and also information about the participants’ profile. Moreover, they created a list of indicative questions for guiding the semi-structured interview during the sessions, and also, highlighted some points regarding the ethical framework and the data management.

The co-creation sessions were facilitated and then transcribed by the lab's research personnel and aimed to gather input from healthcare professionals and patients on the challenges and opportunities of transitional care. Through these sessions, the researchers were able to gain valuable insights and perspectives from those directly involved in the healthcare system.

In particular, the first co-creation session was composed of seven healthcare professionals, including specialists in cardiology, surgery, psychology, and general medicine, aged between 20-45 and having 2-25 years of clinical practice. This session was held in the settings of the “Hippokration” General Hospital of Thessaloniki in the English language. A semi-structured interview guide was used, including open key questions, introductory questions, and transition questions, focusing on difficulties in discharge and transfer processes for older patients with complex care needs, patients’ perceptions of discharge and transfer, resources required for optimal transfers, and how these difficulties are alleviated. The initial qualitative thematic analysis of the insights gained during this co-creation session, highlighted a lack of communication among key healthcare actors, which makes

difficult for them to discharge and transfer older people with complicated needs. Heart failure, stroke, and neurological disorders were the most often mentioned chronic care diseases requiring transitional care and the severity of the problem was one of the most often mentioned grounds for moving patients from the hospital to transitional care. The patients' perceptions of discharge and transitions were primarily attributed to their knowledge of the recommended treatment regimens.

Figure 2 Snapshot - Co-creation session with healthcare professionals

The second co-creation session consisted of 10 members of the AUTH LL community, aged between 65-90, and it was conducted in AUTH living environment simulation in the Greek language, with the support of the VITALISE research team. For this session, a combination of validated standardized questionnaires and a list of guiding questions was used, in relation to chronic care and quality of life. In total, almost all the participants expressed an overall good health and mental status, good quality of life and, also, a good level in operating daily activities, walking and taking care of themselves. However, there were some participants who expressed being slightly anxious or having slight symptoms of depression during the past period.

Figure 3 Snapshot - Co-creation session with older adults

2.2.1.1.2 Conclusions and Future Outlook

In a nutshell, the "Gold Health Care" project is commendable for its holistic approach to healthcare for vulnerable older adults. By incorporating a three-stage process, from preliminary analysis to tailored interventions and evaluations, the project aims to address the multifaceted needs of this demographic. The project's emphasis on creating a local knowledge framework and understanding barriers, facilitators and needs among vulnerable groups ensures that interventions and policies are grounded in real-world insights.

The visit to the AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab and the engagement in co-creation sessions demonstrate a practical approach to integrating technology into healthcare. The utilization of resources in the lab allowed researchers to explore innovative solutions in collaboration with healthcare professionals and older adults.

The insights gained from the co-creation sessions with the healthcare professionals and the older adults provided valuable qualitative data. The identification of a lack of communication among healthcare actors as well as the identified challenges in discharge and transfer processes for older patients with complex care needs, highlighted two particular issues that are crucial and need attention in transitional care. The immediate aftermath involves synthesizing insights from co-creation sessions and using them to inform interventions.

Moreover, the successful co-creation sessions and the insights gained, laid the foundation for the researchers' idea to expand their research study by conducting additional co-creation sessions at the University of Vlore "Ismail Qemali" in Albania and compare the insights collected. By expanding their network, possibly involving more healthcare institutions, community organizations, or academic partners, the researchers aim to enhance the project's impact.

In conclusion, the collaboration between the University of Vlore and AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab in Thessaloniki exemplifies international cooperation in research. Future ventures may include expanding collaborations, disseminating findings through joint publications, and addressing identified challenges in transitional care, contributing that way to the broader healthcare community's knowledge and may attract interest from other researchers or organizations.

2.2.1.1.3 TA Evaluation

To support the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager who was also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), two Ethics & Security Managers were involved, also two Administrative & Financial Managers, one technical expert, one psychologist and some other supportive LL personnel (4 more people). In total, approximately 117 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of "Gold Health Care" project in AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab, both in person and remotely, which is translated to around 13 person days.

In the evaluation questionnaire, all the visiting researchers declared that the output of the TA was much better than expected, even though they had very high expectations before the beginning of their study. In advance, they had mainly indicated that through this TA, they would like to gain knowledge and expertise regarding LL infrastructures, fostering that way their skills in research implementation and transferring this knowledge to their country. Regarding the Fast Track Training Program, all the researchers pointed out that it was much better than expected and that all the training blocks were of very high quality and usefulness. They highlighted that it was very practical for them and facilitated them to make the connection of the theory with some more practical aspects of Living Labs. Most of the Living Lab services provided during TA (understand end-users needs and problems, methodological support and guidance, selection/recruitment of test persons, expertise/support with end-users, physical infrastructure) were rated very high in terms of quality. Key strengths of AUTH LL comprised the multidisciplinary research team and very good organization of the infrastructure which facilitate their access for conducting their study.

"HESTIA" project – ID21

Participant researchers: Theofanis Fotis (lead applicant) - University of Brighton, UK
Afroditi Mara Konidari, Rui Zhang - Tendertec Ltd, UK

2.2.1.1.4 Project summary

The HESTIA project, named after the AI-powered platform developed by Tendertec, aims to assess the platform's potential in assisting and enhancing informal, i.e., unpaid, caregiving and overall well-being. Considering the demographic shift in Europe that is expected to emerge between 2019 and 2050, with the elderly population aged 65 and over projected to increase from 20% to 28.5%, there is an urgent need for long-term care support. As this growth will lead to a considerable rise in the old-age dependency ratio, the reliance on informal care services will be even more pronounced, with families predominantly shouldering caregiving responsibilities due to limited formal support. The lack of a comprehensive strategy and support system underscores the urgency to address the growing demands for long-term care and the welfare of informal caregivers. This project, i.e., real-life testing of the platform for feedback (feasibility and usability) collection constitutes a first step towards shedding a light on the impact unpaid care has on informal caregivers and hopefully influencing policy.

In the context of this TA, three external researchers, Dr Afroditi Mara Konidari and Rui Zhang from Tendertec Ltd in the UK, and Dr Theofanis Fotis from the University of Brighton in the UK, visited the AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab in Thessaloniki, Greece. The visit period for the Tendertec-affiliated researchers was 10-13 January 2024 and 21-24 February 2024, while Dr. Fotis visited the Living Lab infrastructure on 13-16 February 2024. For the purposes of the project, 8 people were recruited from all walks of life, 4 informal caregivers, i.e., not receiving payment for their "services", and their paired care receivers who were over the age of 60.

Hestia is a privacy-preserving care support platform that does not use wearables or cameras and captures missed hazards and early exacerbation symptoms. More specifically, Tendertec's thermal sensors are fitted inside living spaces and collect data about movements. By implementing machine learning algorithms on the thermal sensors' data, HESTIA detects falls, seizures, daily activities, and body temperature trends. HESTIA operates to support informal caregivers by alerting them, through their accompanying app, of missed incidents, fall-risk behaviours, changes in daily living activity (e.g., sleeping, activity levels, night wandering, eating & drinking) and early symptoms of disease exacerbation (e.g., abnormal body temperature) to prevent small issues from escalating into bigger problems. Additionally, they provide the caretakers with the opportunity to reconstruct and review any incident reports to understand not just when it happened, but also why and how it happened, which are key factors for the prevention of further incidents.

The study lasted six weeks. In the first week, the HESTIA sensors were installed in the homes of the care receivers (one sensor per participant, which was installed in their main living space i.e., living room or study), and pre-interviews were conducted with the caregivers and the elders to understand their needs and expectations. Additionally, the caregivers, who were the main test users, were onboarded on the app after a comprehensive assessment questionnaire. In the following two weeks, the caregivers were fully onboarded, while detailed baseline measurements were captured via detailed questionnaires. In these two weeks, any issues with the sensors were addressed. Weeks four and five were dedicated to sharing HESTIA system reports with the caregivers collecting their feedback on system performance and utility and addressing sensor-related concerns while supporting app usage efficiency. Furthermore, on week 4, one member of the external research team conducted onsite qualitative data collection through focus groups with the carers and one-on-one interviews with the care receivers. The final week (week 6) was dedicated to device uninstallations and exit interviews with the participants to gauge their overall experience with the HESTIA system.

Figure 4 Snapshots - Sensor installations

Regarding the needs and expectations of participants, it became evident that female elder were primarily focused on, with varied levels of independence observed, ranging from complete autonomy to dependence due to health issues like vision problems and frailty. Additionally, during the pre-interviews, most of the care receivers' suggestions for improvement of care ranged from more medical check-ups to improved transport options and more services for the elderly. The elders faced challenges related to health issues and varying levels of digital literacy, expressing desires for improved healthcare services and increased autonomy. Themes of health-related challenges and digital literacy emerged consistently, reflecting elders' aspirations for enhanced healthcare and autonomy. The caretakers' suggestions reflected those of the elders, emphasizing the importance of independence and autonomy of the elders. The lack of time is a pervasive issue, causing caregivers to struggle in finding adequate time to support their loved ones. As a result, caregiving often becomes a shared responsibility within the family, with the primary burden falling on those living closest to the elders. Family caregivers often work until late, limiting the time they have available to check in with family and friends until later in the day, this lifestyle introduces the challenge of balancing their caregiving duties with their personal life and work commitments. They express a desire for more flexible working hours, peace of mind through technology, more free time, more support from other family members, and additional technological support to monitor the elders.

Regarding feedback for the system and application, the caretakers highlighted that HESTIA provided them with added reassurance and peace of mind. The perceived usefulness of the platform depends on the right fit between a user's needs and the platform's features. It came to light that when the elder is fairly independent or has 24/7 care, the system does not provide new insights. Regarding the accompanying application, the users found the incident reporting and reconstruction very useful, especially in the cases where the elder maintained a higher level of independence, such as living alone. Users also appreciated the weekly reports presenting key statistics and comparison data. Additionally, the incident reconstructions, as shared via the app, were found to be very useful in initiating conversations with the elderly. Users suggested that clearer guidelines for setting up the app and password would be very helpful, along with providing information about which devices are compatible with the app and highlighted that improving the clarity of reconstructions would be nice. Lastly, most caregivers underlined the importance of having real-time alerts of incidents like falls, with this service being graded as higher in importance than daily monitoring.

Figure 5 Snapshots - HESTIA project researchers

2.2.1.1.5 Conclusions and Future Outlook

Feedback on the Hestia platform underscored several key points. Although the setup process generally proceeded smoothly, recommendations were made to enhance the explanation of this process within the app itself, especially for users less familiar with technology. The perceived value of Hestia relied heavily on how well it matched the user's requirements and the platform's capabilities, with incident reporting and reconstruction proving particularly beneficial, notably for caregivers supporting independent elders. Users appreciated the reporting format, which included a concise summary report and incident reconstructions, finding it helpful for facilitating discussions with the elderly. They stressed that Hestia's efficacy peaked when customized to fit individual circumstances, with real-time alerts being especially prized for accident prevention. Nonetheless, some users observed constraints when elders were relatively independent or under constant care. In summary, while Hestia furnishes essential information for caregivers, its efficacy hinges on aligning with user needs, prompting an ongoing cycle of feedback and enhancements to optimize its utility.

Looking towards future outlooks, this collaboration has the potential to open new avenues for research and policymaking. By leveraging the insights gained from the onboarding activities and feedback from caregivers and elders, researchers can develop more tailored interventions and solutions to address the challenges faced by elderly individuals and their caregivers. Additionally, this collaboration can contribute to the formulation of policies aimed at supporting caregivers and improving the overall well-being of the elderly population. And this need not reflect only one population as the multicentric nature of this collaboration allows the exploration of transcultural differences, as well as the effect of infrastructure differences. Continuous feedback and improvement, as highlighted in the feedback regarding Hestia, will be crucial in ensuring that these efforts remain aligned with the evolving needs of the users and continue to deliver value.

2.2.1.1.6 TA Evaluation

To support the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager who was also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), two Ethics & Security Managers were involved, also two Administrative & Financial Managers, one technical expert and some other supportive LL personnel (2 more people). In total, approximately 121 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of "HESTIA" project in AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab, both in person and remotely, which is translated to around 29 person days.

Overall, the feedback from the researchers on their experience in the AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab was very positive. All the researchers reported that the outcome of the TA was somewhat or much higher than expected and that they are very likely to recommend the Transnational Access to their colleagues or other researchers. The researchers also felt that the inclusion of the Fast Track Training during the Transnational Access was very useful, and they rated as high or very high the quality of all the services provided by the hosted Living Lab, especially in terms of support and

expertise and in understanding the needs and problems of end-users. They only emphasized the idea of having the opportunity for longer piloting (or for real time engagement with users remotely) to validate the obtained results with a wider group of stakeholders, as well as to have the ability to access and share data from other LLs. The key strengths of this experience that the researchers reported to have valued most were the organisation of the AUTH LL and the research team who supported them throughout the realization of their project, as well as the access to LL infrastructures, end-users and knowledge, relevant to cocreation and testing that was required for their experiment.

"DSCS" project – ID35

2.2.1.1.7 Project summary

Participant researchers: Alessio Antonini (lead applicant), Iman Naja - Open University, UK

The current study, named "Digital Support for Cancer Survivors: Opportunities for Software, Agents, and Robotics Intervention" aimed to validate the design of the AI model for 'intelligent companions developed in the UK within the different Greek context, which would be capable of life-long support by alleviating the burden of self-management in a life-long setting, with the broader aim to support the vision of self-driven healthcare.

This entails implementing, expanding, and evolving solutions for preventions and interventions, both software related and those involving autonomous robotics agents. In this context, a second aim was to scope the requirements for autonomous robotics agents that would be involved in at-home care to support self-management and independent living for cancer survivors. In particular, according to previous literature, digital health management has proven beneficial during trials, but the resulting technologies have shown low acceptance and uptake. One of the objectives of this project was to study the design flaws of such technologies that lead to their low acceptance and uptake, taking into consideration the unmet needs of patients and survivors as well as the socio-cultural aspects of the deployment of such technologies.

For the purposes of this TA, two researchers, Alessio Antonini (lead applicant) and Iman Naja from the Open University-United Kingdom visited AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab in Thessaloniki, Greece. The visiting period in the infrastructure for Iman Naja was between the 20th of September 2023 until the 14th of October 2023 and between the 2nd of October 2023 until the 7th of October 2023 for Alessio Antonini.

During the visiting period in the AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab the aim was to gain insights from the participants (cancer patients and survivors, health care professionals and informal caregivers) through co-creation workshops, semi-structured interviews, expert consultations, and advisory services. Each workshop conducted, was divided into three sections. In the first section, the participants were given a presentation about the research and the state of the art. In the second and third sections, the participants were asked indicative questions, which they would answer creating opportunities for conversations and dialogues among the participants themselves and between them and the workshop facilitator. The second section revolved around mHealth and uHealth and the third section revolved around robotic interventions.

In total, three focus group workshops took place, aimed to verify researchers' previous findings and compare or elicit findings within the different Greek context. The first workshop was conducted online with healthcare providers, where four healthcare providers were invited, however, only two doctors were able to participate. The second was conducted in a hybrid manner with six technology experts from the AUTH LL. The final workshop was with three cancer survivors from the Hellenic Association of Women with Breast Cancer "Alma Zois" Thessalonikis.

The key findings included acknowledging the shift towards the reliance on these technologies as well as benefits the technologies provide. The barriers that still need to be overcome focused on the necessity to involve patients and healthcare providers in the iterative processes of technology development, the need to alleviate worries surrounding the introduction of such technologies and resistance to it, where the healthcare providers worry about disruption to their processes and added

workload and the patients worry about a distance being put between them and the healthcare providers as well as their privacy.

Overall, the researchers stressed that the workshops with health care professionals, technology experts, and cancer survivors allowed them to identify common challenges and highlight the similarities - across the two different countries, UK and Greece, and the different projects - of the issues of support.

Similar to the UK, healthcare providers expressed reluctance to introduce the technology within their processes unless it is recommended by the national healthcare service, is not costly, and would not disrupt their routines or add to their workload. Regarding patients, they expressed similar views to those in the UK in terms of fear that the technology would break their connection with their healthcare providers as they would always prefer a direct meaningful connection with their healthcare system as opposed to relying on technology. This is particularly applicable to receiving or discussing information related to their diagnosis, treatment, and recovery, as the patients prefer this to be done only with the healthcare providers. Finally, regarding technology experts, similarities in challenges were found, particularly in terms of the acceptance of technology by patients and health professionals, as well as the difficulties arising from a lack of data.

Figure 6 Snapshots - DSCS project

2.2.1.1.8 Conclusions and Future Outlook

In conclusion, the project's goal of supporting cancer survivors through lifelong self-management using AI, software, and autonomous robotics agents is commendable. The emphasis on prevention and interventions throughout a person's life demonstrates a holistic approach to healthcare beyond immediate treatment phases. Acknowledging the low acceptance and uptake of digital health technologies, the project aimed to understand design flaws and unmet needs. This reflects a user-centric approach, recognizing that successful implementation requires addressing both technological shortcomings and the socio-cultural aspects of deployment. The use of co-creation workshops, semi-structured interviews, expert consultations and advisory services during the visiting period at AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab showcases a comprehensive methodological approach. Engaging with diverse stakeholders, including cancer survivors, healthcare professionals and technology experts, provides a multifaceted perspective. The key findings from the workshops highlighted the shift towards technology reliance, recognizing benefits, but also barriers that need overcoming. In that sense, the emphasis on involving patients and healthcare providers in the iterative development process is a crucial insight, emphasizing the importance of collaborative design. The cross-cultural validation of the AI models and intelligent companions designed in the UK within the Greek context is considered essential for ensuring the adaptability and effectiveness of digital health solutions across different socio-cultural settings. Future ventures could focus on iterative development, collaboration with national healthcare services, and comprehensive evaluations to ensure relevance, and enhance the acceptability and adoption of digital health interventions.

The collaborative research effort between researchers from the Open University, UK and the AUTH Living Environment Simulation within the VITALISE project, promoted knowledge exchange and opened new avenues for future collaborative projects, with an emphasis on an AI-based model for supporting survivors of cancer. Opportunities for joint academic publications are currently being explored, with the aim of integrating new findings with previous findings to provide a complete picture of the challenges and needs of researchers, technology experts, patients and healthcare providers.

2.2.1.1.9 TA Evaluation

For supporting the execution of this TA, several professionals of the LL staff were actively engaged. In particular, apart from the LL manager who was also the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL), two Ethics & Security Managers were involved, also two Administrative & Financial Managers, two technical experts, two doctors and some other supportive LL personnel (5 more people). In total, approximately 123 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of "DSCS" project in AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab, both in person and remotely, which is translated to around 33 person days.

In the evaluation questionnaire, both visiting researchers reported that the output of the TA was higher than expected and that it is very likely that they recommend the TA experience to their colleagues or other researchers. Prior to their visit, the researchers had mainly indicated that through this TA they would like to gain and validate new findings and insights related to socio-cultural characteristics of stakeholders, as well as access state of the art research facilities. After the completion of the TA, the researchers reported that the key-strength of this experience was the knowledge transfer from different expertise and the administrative support provided by the hosting LL. The only suggestion for the TA improvement by one out of the two researchers was to reduce, if possible, the filling forms and evaluation questionnaires requested. Regarding the Fast Track Training Program, the researchers declared that it was useful and of high importance and they also rated very highly the quality of the services provided by the hosted Living Lab, especially in terms of understanding the needs and problems of end-users and providing methodological support and guidance.

2.2.2 INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room

INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room Living Lab has completed a total of two (2) Transnational Access projects in the period from April to October 2023. A total of four (4) researchers visited the INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab, three (of four initially planned) belonging to TA ID13 focusing in Investigating Kinematic Outputs in Immersive 3D, VR Environments, and one belonging to TA ID42 addressing the use of Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality for Early Dementia Detection.

Project	TA period	TA Services	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	N° of researchers	Visit performed
VirtuaLearn (ID13)	April-June 23	<i>Living lab project planning and management, Capacity building Expert opinion and advisory services, Access to data, Co-creation session, Concept and proof-of-concept tests, Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, Simulation test & Usability testing</i>	50	0	3	Yes

IDENTIA (ID42)	Sep-Oct. 23	<i>Living lab project planning and management, Expert opinion and advisory services, Co-creation session, Simulation test, Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, Usability testing</i>	22	14	1	Yes
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Table 2 INTRAS VR/AR Environment and Snoezelen Room LL Projects – Current Status

“VirtualLearn” project- Neural aspects of motor learning in a fully immersive VR environment – ID13

Participant Researchers: Luka Slozar (lead applicant), Uros Marusic, Manca Peskar (Science and Research Centre Koper, Institute for Kinesiology Research, Slovenia) - Science and Research Centre Koper, Slovenia

(note: initially the Agreement for Transnational Access signed included a fourth researcher, Aleksandar Miladinovic)

2.2.2.1.1 Project summary

This project is focused on understanding the mechanisms involved in learning movement kinematic output in an immersive 3D virtual reality (VR) environment. The goal is to advance the ecological validity of research in motor control by using immersive technologies like Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs) and Cave Automatic Virtual Environments (CAVE). The Fitts Law Model, a well-established predictive model of motor learning, will be translated from 2D to a fully immersive 3D VR setting. The project further aims to harness the potential of technologies like mobile brain/body imaging (MoBI) and telemedicine to study and facilitate the rehabilitation process. Ultimately, the project aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge in the intersection of motor learning, neurophysiology, and VR, and to potentially enhance rehabilitation techniques using immersive technologies.

The acceptance of this TA by the Living Lab was under conditions. The researchers initially required having from the Living Lab a fully dedicated software developer with experience with Unity to work full-time on the project and develop the Fitts Law Model, but this was not feasible. After discussion with the team and understanding that without a full-time software developer on the team, it was not feasible to create the Fitts' Law program from scratch as the external researchers initially planned. Due to this limitation, changes were made to the research plans. Thus, the interaction took a different, albeit equally beneficial, form. Instead, Gradior Multisensorial app developed by INTRAS & IDES S.L. was an instrumental case study for the research team. This immersive Virtual Reality (VR) tool applies a snoezelen multisensory stimulation approach, aiming to enhance emotional well-being and behavioural regulation.

The external researchers performed the TA fully remote, for which the LL team established weekly communication meetings. Following the introductory meeting where the study proposal was presented, the LL shared their Extended Reality (XR) based interventions, outlining key components and unique features of digital interventions. Additionally, the LL provided Luka Šlosar with the means to remotely test these interventions using their own VR headset. Several participants were engaged to undergo the interventions, their valuable feedback collected for further refinement. The researchers were provided with a license for testing, and several meetings were held to discuss the practical implementation of the tool and the effects previously observed in studies. A workshop was also held to introduce the scientific basis of the VR multisensory approach, a demo session and further discussion.

Concurrently, Luka developed the first draft of the study protocol, which was subsequently reviewed in collaboration with LL experts. After the incorporation of suggested adjustments, the definitive version gained approval from the LL experts during the conclusive meeting.

As a senior research expert, Uroš assumed a supervisory role, guiding and refining Luka's drafting of the research protocol. He conducted a comprehensive analysis of the feedback garnered from the pilot study, executed utilizing LL's XR interventions, and delineated imperative procedural enhancements for its seamless implementation across a larger participant cohort.

Uroš engaged in a collaborative review process alongside LL experts, culminating in the meticulous refinement of the final research protocol. This joint effort also paved the way for the exploration of potential future collaborative research initiatives and studies in conjunction with the LL.

Manca Peskar as a neurorehabilitation expert, has provided a comprehensive exploration of the potential applications of XR interventions for achieving cognitive improvements. Furthermore, she has undertaken an in-depth examination of the feasibility of integrating electroencephalography (EEG) measurements to discern functional brain changes induced by XR interventions.

These concepts and possibilities were subject to examination and discussion with LL experts, fostering a collaborative exchange of insights and expertise. Subsequently, EEG measurements underwent rigorous testing and evaluation within the Slovenian Lab. The preliminary feasibility data underwent rigorous analysis under Manca's supervision. Following this analysis, results were presented and deliberated with LL experts, culminating in strategic discussions concerning the roadmap for conducting a study involving a more extensive participant cohort.

The information and experience exchange proved valuable as it served as a foundation for the team's own prototype. Building on these insights, the research team is currently developing a study that is expected to commence towards the end of the year. The lessons learned from this process play a significant role in shaping the design and implementation of this upcoming study.

In brief, final refined focus was on gaining experience with the VR environments and tasks used in the LL, building upon the research team new study protocol using the knowledge acquired from that experience.

2.2.2.1.2 Conclusions and Future Outlook

The Transnational Access (TA) project, initially poised to explore the intricacies of learning movement kinematic output within immersive 3D virtual reality (VR) environments, encountered a pivotal shift towards the exchange of the knowledge of the LL team and testing of the Extended Reality (XR) based interventions. This recalibration from a focus on the Fitts Law Model in a 3D VR setting to the adoption of snoezelen multisensory stimulation for studying emotional well-being and behavioral regulation represents a strategic and adaptive response to project constraints. Despite these changes, the project's integrity was not only preserved but also enriched by a deepened practical experience with VR environments and tasks. This experience informed the development of a novel study protocol, marking a significant leap in the practical application of VR technologies for research. The collaborative efforts and the iterative process of feedback and refinement with the Living Lab (LL) have laid a solid foundation for future studies, potentially contributing to novel insights in motor learning, neurophysiology, and rehabilitation through immersive technologies.

As the research team embarks on their forthcoming study, the lessons learned from their engagement with the Grador Multisensorial app and the XR environments promise to influence the design and implementation significantly. This study is expected to integrate the insights gained on behavioral regulation and emotional well-being enhancement within XR settings, potentially pioneering new methodologies and applications in the field. The exploration of mobile brain/body imaging (MoBI) and telemedicine in conjunction with XR technologies remains a promising avenue for advancing rehabilitation processes. The project's experiences underscore the importance of adaptability and the value of practical application experience in navigating the complexities of technological research. Moving forward, the research team is poised to contribute to the growing body of knowledge surrounding the application of immersive technologies in health and rehabilitation, with a keen eye on enhancing methodological approaches and participant engagement strategies. The dissemination of research findings through rigorous review, ethical evaluations, and publications in peer-reviewed journals will ensure that the project's contributions are recognized and integrated

into future research and practice, driving forward the boundaries of motor control, neurophysiology, and rehabilitation research.

2.2.2.1.3 TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a dedicated team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). Support included a Technical Manager, a Psychologist, an Administrative Manager, two software developers (the second as a substitute), and a Technical Expert. In total, approximately 106 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of the VirtualLearn research in the INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room Living Lab, in a remote Transnational Access. This is translated to around 13 person days.

In the post-Transnational Access (TA) survey, researchers shared the most positive feedback, giving a perfect score for recommending the TA to others. The TA not only met but exceeded expectations, offering substantial outcomes that greatly surpassed initial predictions. The Fast Track Training program proved highly effective, rated with very high usefulness, playing a key role in enhancing research productivity. The lead research mentioned to have “acquired valuable knowledge on effectively applying research in practical ways to support the community and open up new avenues for practical skills and programs”. One note made, was that, although the external research team limitations reduced the TA to a remote format, researchers admitted that in-person would undoubtedly add extra value. A standout aspect was the invaluable advice on implementing digital interventions for elderly populations, highlighting the TA's supportive and collaborative nature. The hosting Living Lab's services, including expert methodological support, received positive ratings for their quality. The Vitalise tools, such as the Data Tool and Panel Management tool, were notably beneficial. Researchers anticipate these resources will be vital in their future work, indicating the TA's enduring impact on their research. With no suggestions for improvement, their responses reflect general satisfaction with the TA experience.

This collective feedback emphasizes the TA's effectiveness in delivering essential training, support, and resources, significantly aiding the researchers' endeavors. The TA served as a pivotal learning and ideation platform for developments and research related to XR environments, showcasing its success in fostering innovation and expanding professional networks.

“IDENTIA” project - Early Dementia Detection through VR and AI – ID42

Participant researcher: Fátima Gonzalez Palau, Gonzalez Palau Center for Psychotherapy, Neuropsychology and Neurorehabilitation, Argentina

2.2.2.1.4 Project summary

IDENTIA project focused on starting the development of a screening system based on Virtual Reality technologies for the identification of preclinical phases of dementia applying machine learning and deep learning techniques.

The IDENTIA project addresses the global urgency of early dementia detection using AI and VR technologies. Through predictive models using cognitive indicators, the project aims to diagnose dementia at the preclinical phases, leveraging neuropsychological assessments in a virtual environment. This novel method presents a cost-effective, non-invasive, and highly sensitive approach to early detection, promising a significant improvement in patient quality of life.

Access to the INTRAS Living Lab allowed the IDENTIA project to benefit from the lab's therapeutic VR research and extensive experience in geriatric and palliative care services. The lab, equipped with advanced IT software and devices for training, rehabilitation, and daily living assistance, is an ideal setting for fostering the project's digital cognitive assessments, facilitating a pre-validation of the research premises in real living and working environments, in the course of the project committed to developing more effective early detection methods.

This is invaluable in optimizing the project's strategies, for later carrying out experimental studies involving a sample of 200 older adults, and ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of early dementia

detection methods, moving us closer towards a more sustainable and responsive healthcare system in the face of demographic challenges.

Transnational access was conducted remotely during weeks 1 and 4 (from September 11th to September 22nd and from October 7th to 11th), while weeks 2 and 3 (from September 24th to October 7th) involved face-to-face interactions.

The TA Project kicked off with system specifications development, collaborative meetings with developers, and extensive bibliographic research using the PRISMA methodology. Key activities included VR environment testing, protocol reviews, and ethical committee presentations, setting a solid foundation for in-depth exploration and development.

The LL offered expert viewpoints and recommendations to assist the researcher in evaluating the current state and specifications of the IDENTIA system. Furthermore, the system's specifications underwent thorough scrutiny and discussion with LL experts, promoting a collaborative exchange of knowledge and expertise.

Additionally, the LL provided the opportunity to assess the system's user-friendliness. Prior to the testing phase, several specialized meetings were organized to address the intricacies of the application, clarify the methodologies governing its utilization, explore strategies for data utilization, and gather feedback from LL patients.

During the in-person TA, after arriving at INTRAS, the researcher engaged in user testing and evaluation, applying a participatory approach to assess usability and the system's predictive capabilities involving 5 Professionals from Neuropsychology Clinics and 6 older adults. Following the pilot usability testing, the results were subjected to analysis and consultation with LL experts.

Figure 7 Snapshots - User testing and evaluation

A visit to the Casaverde Valladolid Rehabilitation Center and collaborative publication writing further deepened the project's clinical and research dimensions.

The last day of the in-person TA marked a great surprise with a session delivered by the researcher on mindfulness and neuroscience to the INTRAS Living Lab Team, emphasizing resilience and well-being. This session, provided insights and practical strategies for applying these principles in both personal and professional contexts, enhancing the team's development and well-being.

Figure 8 Snapshots - Mindfulness and neuroscience session

The final phase was conducted remotely focused on refining the predictive approach, measuring VR test timings, and conducting an in-depth scientific literature review on early dementia diagnosis. This comprehensive review and ongoing system development culminated in the completion of literature review and system specifications.

2.2.2.1.5 Conclusions and Future Outlook

This TA project undertook a comprehensive review of scientific literature, highlighting the potential of subtle cognitive indicators and cutting-edge technologies for early diagnosis in neurosciences. Partnering with the INTRAS Living Lab was pivotal, enriching the project with expert opinions and fostering an environment conducive to innovation. Through participatory approaches and usability testing with end users, IDENTIA fine-tuned its system specifications, incorporating feedback to refine its digital cognitive assessments. This process not only validated the project's research premises but also set a foundation for future experimental studies aimed at enhancing dementia detection methodologies.

Looking ahead, IDENTIA is set to build on its successes and collaborative achievements to enhance and broaden its research scope. The promising results from early usability tests and the partnership with INTRAS Living Lab have set the stage for further experimental studies with a broader group of older adults, essential for assessing the IDENTIA system's real-world applicability and deepening our understanding of early dementia indicators.

Efforts are underway to disseminate the project's pioneering findings through scientific publications and conference presentations. The collaboration with LL was already presented in the XXV Argentine Congress of Neuropsychiatry and Cognitive Neuroscience, held on September 2023. Moreover, the data collected will be presented as a scientific paper that is being performed as a review of state of the art for the Aging and Mental Health Journal. These initiatives aim to not only broadcast IDENTIA novel dementia detection approach but also to encourage wider academic and clinical engagement. Ensuring open access to collected data will allow the broader research community to leverage and expand upon IDENTIA contributions.

As the project moves into its next phase, the focus will be on expanding the system's predictive capabilities, augmenting the system's predictive accuracy, and evaluating commercialization opportunities to broaden access to the IDENTIA screening system for healthcare professionals and patients alike. This journey from concept to implementation exemplifies the value of collaborative research and innovation in healthcare, setting a promising trajectory for future advancements in the field.

2.2.2.1.6 TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a dedicated team from the LL staff was actively involved. The team was led by the LL manager, who also served as the Research Infrastructure Leader (RIL). Support included a Technical Manager, a Psychologist, an Administrative Manager, a

Neuropsychologist, a Data Analyst, a Software Developer, and a Technical Expert. In total, approximately 127 hours were spent by all the professionals for supporting the realization of the IDENTIA research in the INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room Living Lab, in a hybrid Transnational Access. This is translated to around 16 person days.

The researcher strongly recommends the program to peers, noting it surpassed expectations and provided a comprehensive research experience. Highlighted was the Fast Track Training's effectiveness in enhancing the research process.

The Living Lab experience was highlighted as exceeding expectations, with the researcher emphasizing the strong and cooperative relationships formed with professionals and software developers. These relationships facilitated an effective exchange of ideas and significantly contributed to the project's development. The researcher engaged with a wide array of services such as expert opinion, advisory services, co-creation sessions, simulation tests, and usability testing, demonstrating the program's capacity to support diverse research needs.

The Vitalise website emerged as a key informational resource. Discussions with the INTRAS LL Team also touched on the potential of the Vitalise Discovery Portal to support FAIR Data Management and provide access to datasets. This could be crucial for future enhancements of the project, including the refinement of models and improvement of robustness by utilizing available datasets.

2.2.3 Thomas More Experience lab

Two groups of researchers with a total of six (6) applicants requested to perform their Transnational Access project using the Thomas More Experience lab (ID36 & ID61). Unfortunately, one of these projects involving two researchers was cancelled due to medical reasons concerning the lead applicant of the study (ID61). Project ID36 took place in October 2023.

Project	TA period	TA Services	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	N° of researchers	Visit performed
ChatterGlove project (ID36)	October 2023	<i>Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Legal, regulation and safety standard support, Panel management, Intake and matching, Living lab project planning and management, Co-creation session, Prototype testing, Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation, Usability testing</i>	0	60	4	Yes
Virtual Basel project (ID61)	Cancelled due to medical reasons	-	-	-	- (2 applied but the study was cancelled)	No

Table 3 Thomas More Experience lab Projects – Current Status

"ChatterGlove" project – ID36

Participant researchers: Theodor-Radu Grumeza, Dorin Cazan, Richard Baczur, Daniel Miron - West University of Timisoara, Romania

2.2.3.1.1 Project summary

This study was named ChatterGlove – A healthcare appliance for speech/hearing impaired individuals. Individuals with a speech or hearing impairment experience difficulties to communicate

effectively. These impairments can have an impact on their interactions with others, educational opportunities, employment prospects, feelings of isolation and exclusion, and overall quality of life. However, with the implementation of inclusive practices, assistive innovative technologies, and supportive workplace environments, these barriers can be overcome.

One example of such a technological innovation is the ChatterGlove, an exoskeleton that aims to translate sign language into spoken or written text. The core aim of the ChatterGlove is to offer a healthcare appliance that will help speech or hearing-impaired individuals to communicate in a simple manner by using a 3D printed exoskeleton glove, which by means of electronic modules aims to translate hand signals and gestures into written text and speech.

The current study aimed to investigate user experience and user acceptance of the ChatterGlove prototype, an exoskeleton prototype that intends to translate sign language into spoken or written text. In the first part of the study, the focus was user experience and user acceptance of individuals with speech/hearing difficulties. During the second part of the study, which comprised a co-creation session, the goal was to collect feedback about the potential use of the ChatterGlove from technical experts.

During the TA, the visiting researchers managed to implement a novel sensor technology solution for the ChatterGlove. Thomas More technical experts helped improving the prototype by 3D printed parts that made the ChatterGlove more comfortable to wear. The LiCalab panel manager recruited hearing impaired individuals by contacting patient and peer's organisations. In the small-scale real-life testing, 13 individuals with hearing impairment tested the exoskeleton prototype. The LiCalab panel manager facilitated communication between the TA research team and the friend/relative accompanying the hearing-impaired person whenever necessary. This person spoke sign language as well. Visiting researchers used accumulating data to construct a comprehensive dataset tailored for learning novel sign language expressions. They conducted tests encompassing letters, numbers, and conversational scenarios and gathered feedback regarding potential application scenarios. Moreover, an expert session comprising 4 technical experts was organised for demonstration of the ChatterGlove. Perceived usefulness and usability of the device according to individuals with hearing impairment as well as technical experts was evaluated. Although participants liked the fact that researchers were interested in enhancing communication options for hearing impaired individuals and improving their quality of life, some of them preferred to have the community learn how to speak and understand sign language instead.

Figure 9 Snapshot - Attaching the exoskeleton to a hearing-impaired individual

2.2.3.1.2 Conclusions and Future Outlook

The ChatterGlove was developed in Romania and the developers had won a prize at the hackathon of the West University of Timisoara. However, previous tests were performed on colleagues without hearing impairments. In the TA study, the ChatterGlove was used in the target group of individuals speaking sign language for the first time. LiCalab helped the researchers to get in contact with these individuals. This study helped the researchers' enhancing comprehension of end-users' daily needs and challenges. Feedback collected during both parts of the study is used to make improvements to the design process of the ChatterGlove. This assistive innovative technology may improve social interaction and wellbeing of hearing-impaired individuals. The lead applicant informed about possibilities for future recruitment of this target group or performing a research stay at LiCalab for testing an updated version of the prototype.

2.2.3.1.3 TA Evaluation

Several professionals from LiCalab were involved for supporting of the realization of this TA project: One operations manager, one panel manager, one technical expert on exoskeletons and one researcher-psychologist. A total of 137 hours was devoted to the project which is translated to around 17 person days. The majority of the researcher-psychologist time was spent on protocol development and preparing the ethical application. The panel manager recruited the hearing-impaired individuals as well as the technical experts and moderated the prototype testing sessions and expert discussion. Twenty hours spread over 4 days were needed to adjust the ChatterGlove prototype and print 3D parts to make the exoskeleton more flexible and pleasant to wear.

In the evaluation questionnaire, researchers stated that TA output was much higher than expected. They especially appreciated that the researchers working at LiCalab and Mobilab&Care were very well trained helped them a lot with both technical issues as well as the interaction with the hearing-impaired individuals that tested the ChatterGlove.

"Virtual Basel" project – ID61

Participant researchers: Joanna Timilliotis, Nikolas Oswald - University Hospital Basel, Switzerland.

2.2.3.1.4 Project summary

This study, named Immersive Mental Health with Wearable Biofeedback and VR: Virtual Base, combines the use of two Vitalise research infrastructures, namely the THOMAS MORE Motion lab – Mobilab & Care and the THOMAS MORE Experience lab.

Virtual Basel is an immersive mental health project that utilizes virtual reality and wearable biofeedback to provide a calming and therapeutic experience for patients. The project includes 360-degree videos of scenic locations in Basel, which are viewed through VR glasses and accompanied by nature sounds, meditations, or classical music. Wearable devices are used to measure the patient's vital signs and provide biofeedback on the VR glasses, allowing them to actively engage in their relaxation and stress- and pain reduction.

During the Transnational Access (TA), several activities were planned to be carried out, including the development of a prototype that combines Virtual Reality (VR), Wearables and Biofeedback technologies. The prototype was about to be tested for the first time, and its effectiveness would be evaluated. The concept of the prototype would be refined based on the results of the initial testing, and proof-of-concept tests would be conducted to further validate its potential. The insights that would be gained from these activities aimed to help inform future research and development efforts in this field.

The following tools were supposed to be utilized:

- 360° camera (e.g. Insta360° Pro 2)
- VR headset(s) (e.g. Pico Neo 3)
- wearables for monitoring vital signs (Empatica watch)

The data collection would include:

- Physiological responses to stress and pain through wearables: heart rate, respiratory rate, and skin conductance
- Patient-reported outcome measures: validated measures of pain, disability, quality of life, and patient satisfaction
- Qualitative data concerning patient experience and perceptions of the intervention obtained through semi-structured interviews

2.2.3.1.5 Conclusions and Future Outlook

Due to unforeseen health related issues of the lead applicant this project was cancelled. No replacement was found for the supervision of the student involved in this project. Nevertheless, the researchers appreciated the effort of the hosting Living Lab during the preparations of this project. Hence, they are willing to collaborate in future projects.

2.2.3.1.6 TA Evaluation

Unfortunately, the TA for this project was cancelled due to medical reasons regarding the lead applicant.

2.2.4 UPM-LifeSTech- LifeSpace Living Lab

During this period, LifeSpace UPM has completed a total of two (2) Transnational Access projects in the period from October 2023 to December 2023. Finally, LifeSpace UPM has recruited six (6) researchers. Four belonging to TA ID93, and two belonging to TA ID59. However, one member of the TA ID93 team decided to cancel her participation once the agreement was signed. The research team from ID59 submitted an abstract to the VITALISE symposium entitled: “Exploring IADLs in a Smart Home Setting at LifeSpace Living Lab UPM, Madrid”.

Project	TA period	TA Services	TA Days Remote	TA Days in-person	Nº of researchers	Visit performed
Wait Safe validation at LifeSpace Living Lab project (ID93)	23-27 Oct 2023	<i>Small scale piloting, Real settings piloting, Stakeholder engagement, Expert opinion and advisory services, Business cases, User recruitment, Simulation test & Usability testing</i>	0	5	3	Yes
Exploring perceptions to IADLs at LifeSpace Living Lab” project (ID59)	29 Nov – 13 Dec 2023	<i>User recruitment, Small scale piloting, Co-creation sessions, Expert opinion and advisory services</i>	4	0	2	Yes, virtually

Table 4 UPM-LifeSTech-LifeSpace LL Projects – Current Status

"Wait Safe validation at LifeSpace Living Lab” project – ID93

2.2.4.1.1 Project summary

Participant researchers: Paweł Grajkowski, Ewelina Moszyk, Wojciech Witczak, Aleksander Lasecki - PSNC labs, Poznan, Poland

Wait Safe is a patient queue management system used in clinics and hospitals. The aim of the project is to reduce the risk of infection caused by the presence of many people in one room, as well as to improve the well-being of patients and medical staff. Through a web service and screens in waiting rooms, patients and medical personnel have access to the queue progress view. Additionally, the patient can register their phone number and receive a notification about their approaching appointment. Thanks to this solution, patients can leave the waiting room and wait in a location of

their choice, such as a park or cafe, while monitoring their place in the queue using their mobile device. The use of physical RFID cards also makes the system user-friendly for technologically excluded individuals. Sound notifications are also provided in the waiting room to better adapt the system for people with visual impairments. The Wait Safe system also takes care of the well-being of the doctor. An additional functionality is calling patients to the office. With our card readers, the doctor decides when to call the next patient, allowing them to calmly complete medical documentation after the appointment and meet their physiological needs. The medical unit can also collect statistical data resulting from delays and visit length, allowing for better optimization of patient scheduling in individual rooms.

The TA activities extended from October 23 to 27, 2023, and included a series of training activities, feedback sessions, and real-environment testing. Upon their arrival in Madrid, participants were welcomed at the LifeSpace facilities. The program began with rapid training sessions divided into two parts, covering a total of six modules. This intensive training was designed to equip participants with the necessary knowledge and skills for their research activities.

Figure 10 Snapshot - External researchers ID93 attending the FTTP

A significant portion of the TA activities was dedicated to testing in the controlled environment of LifeSpace, fine-tuning the WaitSafe solution, technically testing it, using tablets to implement surveys to collect initial data and opinions, and finally developing educational materials for patients. Once this service was completed, researchers had the opportunity to test the solution in a real environment. Specifically, at the Hospital Clinico San Carlos in the Madrid region, in a waiting room of the cardiology area involving 4 healthcare professionals and 11 patients.

TA also included a feedback consolidation session with healthcare professionals from the Hospital Universitario HM Montepíncipe, a private health institution. This session focused on the Wait Safe solution, gathering ideas and suggestions from experts in the field. The information obtained was of great value for the prototype iteration. Finally, a wrap-up session was held where experiences and feedback were exchanged.

Figure 11 Snapshots - WaitSafe prototype validation in real settings

2.2.4.1.2 Conclusions and Future Outlook

The Wait Safe patient queue management system has been successfully tested in a controlled and real-world environment thanks to the services provided by LifeSpace Living Lab. The system is designed to reduce the risk of infection, improve the well-being of patients and medical staff, and optimize patient scheduling. The TA activities were successful in equipping participants with the necessary knowledge and skills to conduct their research activities and in gathering valuable feedback from healthcare professionals, hospital managers and people involved in the procurement process of this type of solutions in the healthcare systems.

Overall, the TA was completed smoothly although there were a number of attitudes problems among the attendees which created an extra burden for the LL team.

2.2.4.1.3 TA evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a dedicated team from the LL staff was involved. In particular, apart from the LL manager, a technical manager, an administrative manager, a facilitator, a UX/UI expert and a doctor, as well as hospital directors were actively engaged. In total, approximately 212 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of “Wait Safe validation at LifeSpace Living Lab” project in UPM LifeSpace LL, which is translated to around 35 person days.

In the evaluation questionnaire, key highlights from the researchers’ responses include varied likelihood of recommending the Transnational Access, with scores ranging from 8 to 10, indicating generally positive experiences. The feedback on the Fast Track Training program's usefulness varied, with scores between 5 and 7, suggesting room for improvement. Researchers appreciated aspects such as access to real-life testing facilities, research techniques, and feedback from different perspectives. Suggestions for improvement include more involvement of the hosting Living Lab in projects and further steps such as drafting collaborative business models or projects. Various ratings were also noted for the provided services, such as understanding end-user needs, methodological support, and physical infrastructure. Accordingly, Vitalise products, including the Data Tool, Panel Management tool, website, and Wiki page were evaluated for their user-friendliness and usefulness in research processes, with some products were not presented to one of the teams. Future needs for services and products were anticipated to be high across several areas, including understanding end-user needs, methodological support, and physical infrastructure.

Each researcher had specific feedback and suggestions, indicating a tailored experience with the Transnational Access program and identifying areas for improvement and future focus.

"Exploring perceptions to IADLs at LifeSpace Living Lab" project – ID59

2.2.4.1.4 Project summary

Participant researchers: Linda Shore, Sonya Lizbeth Joseph - Digital Health Innovation - Glasgow School of Art

The Moray area is a rural part of Scotland that is experiencing a decline in population and also services. Therefore, the focus is to enhance the lived experience within the community with connectedness and services. The Moray region has a high older adult population. As we age, we tend to spend a longer time in our home, often living with an underlying condition, and a requirement for efficient and accessible comfort and heating. The Digital Health Innovation & Care Centre (DHI) identified that 'Smart housing/communities' would be one of five key Living Lab projects due to an ageing population in the Moray region and a requirement to support people to live well as they age in their own homes.

The activities conducted at the LifeSpace Living Lab as part of the TA activities were designed to explore perceptions related to Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADLs) in a smart house setting, focusing on older adults and the general population's interaction with and perception of various technologies that assist in everyday life activities. Before starting the activities, the LifeSpace Living Lab implemented a recruitment strategy to recruit 10 participants in the study (5 participants +60 years old, 5 participants +30 years old). External researchers were connected remotely.

Once the study started, the external researchers were engaged in Fast Track Training sessions. These sessions were intended to provide them with a foundational understanding or training related to the use of smart technologies within the Living Lab environment. The aim was to prepare the participants for the practical tasks and discussions that would follow, ensuring they had the necessary background to engage meaningfully with the technology.

Following the training, a session regarding ethics was held. This important part of the TA activities focused on addressing any questions or concerns participants might have had regarding the research process. Topics such as informed consent, privacy, and the use of participant data were discussed to ensure clarity and to uphold ethical standards throughout the research.

The core of the activities was around task sessions on various IADLs. These sessions were meticulously designed to cover a wide range of daily living activities and the impact of smart technologies on these activities. In each session, 2 participants (one older, one younger) were there facilitated by the LifeSpace Living Lab manager:

- 1) The Transportation session explored how participants arrange and access transportation using smart technologies. The discussion included considerations around ownership versus the use of alternative transportation methods that are facilitated by smart systems.
- 2) During the Communications session, the focus was on how participants utilize digital and tele-care solutions for healthcare and support. The impact of these technologies on communication and well-being was a key discussion point.
- 3) The Shopping and Food Preparation session examined how participants plan meals, access ingredients, and shop for clothing using smart home technologies. It also explored alternative approaches to consumer services made possible by smart systems.
- 4) A combined session on Financial Management & House Cleaning and Home Maintenance addressed how participants use smart technologies for bill payment, financial assets management, estate planning, as well as house cleaning and maintenance tasks. Insights into the convenience and challenges of these tools, and the role of smart systems in maintaining a safe and comfortable living environment were gathered.
- 5) The Managing Medications session investigated how participants access prescriptions and medications using smart home technologies, exploring the impact on medication adherence and health outcomes.

Throughout these activities, expressions and findings were documented on a Miro board, building an understanding of user experience and interactions regarding the IADL sessions. This approach facilitated a comprehensive exploration of the role of emerging and existing technologies in enhancing the daily living activities of older adults and the general population within a smart house context, ensuring a rich and informative research experience. Finally, the sessions were recorded for research purposes and LifeSpace Living Lab team did the transcripts to be sent back to the external researchers.

Figure 12 Snapshots - External researchers ID59 & participants at LifeSpace Living Lab

2.2.4.1.5 Conclusions and Future Outlook

The LifeSpace Living Lab activities were well executed. Through a series of well-structured sessions focused on Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADLs), the LifeSpace Living Lab has provided valuable insights into how technology can improve transportation, communication, shopping, food preparation, financial management, household cleaning, home maintenance and medication management.

Engagement with participants through a mix of training, task execution and ethical discussions ensured the right approach to assessing the role of smart technology in everyday life. This approach not only highlighted the current state of technology adoption among different age groups, but also highlighted potential barriers, benefits and areas for improvement, which external researchers valued positively. The use of a Miro board for documentation and reflection further enriched the external researchers' understanding of and interaction with these technologies. Despite the fact that the external researchers were on remote, and the spoken language was Spanish, the TA activities were smooth and appreciated.

2.2.4.1.6 TA Evaluation

To facilitate the execution of this TA, a dedicated team from the LL staff was involved. In particular, apart from the LL manager, a technical manager, an administrative manager, a facilitator and a UX/UI expert were actively engaged. In total, approximately 134 hours were spent by all the aforementioned professionals for supporting the realization of “Exploring perceptions to IADLs at LifeSpace Living Lab” project in UPM LifeSpace LL, which is translated to around 31 person days.

Regarding the evaluation questionnaires, the two visiting researchers were engaged in activities focused on exploring the role of smart technologies in supporting Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADLs). Both researchers found the inclusion of a Fast Track Training program highly beneficial, with scores of 9 and 8 out of 10, respectively, indicating its usefulness in preparing participants for the tasks. Both also appreciated the clear and adaptive communications from the UPM team and had no suggestions for improvements, highlighting the effectiveness of the program's execution and support provided.

Researchers anticipate a continuous need for understanding end-user needs, methodological support, recruitment of test persons, expertise with end users, and physical infrastructure. They also highlighted the usefulness of data tools and panel management tools in their research, suggesting these will remain essential in future work. An interesting insight was the expressed interest in VR technology for future research needs, pointing towards an expanding scope for digital and immersive technologies in healthcare research.

3 Discussion

The following sections offer an overview of the WP9 TA results, as well as a reflective analysis including overall LL experience of the Living Labs in relation to the TAs, distilling lessons learnt and experience gained throughout the process, as well as insightful information about the services utilized during the TA research studies.

3.1 Overall results

In the infographic below the Transnational Access performed within WP9 - Living Lab infrastructures for transitional care is presented. The infographic includes aggregated information from the three (3) VITALISE Open calls, taking into account all the executed and cancelled projects.

Figure 13 Infographic for the TA to LL infrastructures for transitional care research studies

As shown from the infographic, the number of participants reached is 27 applicants, from which 1 TA was cancelled due to medical reasons and 2 members of the research team did not participate due to personal reasons. From the 27 total number of applicants, 14 were males and 13 females, achieving a great proportion of gender balance and inclusivity. Furthermore, the research domains of the applicants are presented, with almost 82% coming from academia and 18% coming from industry. The working countries of the applicants are also presented. The TAs performed within WP9 reached applicants from 6 different working countries in Europe and Latin America. In particular, we reached applicants from Albania, Slovenia, the UK, Romania, Argentina and Poland.

3.2 AUTH Health care transition Living Lab

Overall, the experience gained from the TA projects at AUTH Health care transition Living Lab underscores positive aspects in communication and collaboration with engaged researchers, fostering a productive and effective working relationship. Frequent and effective communications between researchers and the LL staff contributed to the overall success of the projects, showcasing willingness and flexibility from both parties. While there were no major issues, some internal administrative and managerial challenges, particularly related to bilateral agreement signing, caused delays. Valuable lessons include the importance of early clarification and discussion of critical points with the relevant administrative departments to streamline processes. To enhance efficiency, future TA projects could benefit from having all necessary documents, questionnaires, and templates prepared and printed in advance. Additionally, addressing external researchers' low responsiveness to emails prior to the in-person visit by implementing more frequent and proactive communication strategies could mitigate delays. The experience also revealed challenges in participant recruitment, suggesting the need for a proactive approach, including early stakeholder mapping, advanced recruitment planning, and the anticipation of potential difficulties to ensure a smoother execution of future TA projects. In summary, the TA projects at AUTH Health care transition Living Lab provided

valuable insights into successful collaboration while identifying specific areas for improvement, ultimately contributing to a more streamlined and effective process for future endeavors.

Moreover, during the realization of the various TA projects at AUTH Health care transition Living Lab, it became apparent that several LL services were extensively utilized to facilitate various phases of the research process. Initially, during the early stages of the TA projects, the most frequently employed services were expert opinion and advisory services, providing crucial guidance and insights. This was complemented by capacity building to enhance researchers' skills and knowledge relevant to their specific research topic and interests. In the subsequent phase of project planning and management, services such as intake and matching, legal, regulation, and safety standard support, along with panel management were prominently utilized. The ongoing testing & validation process saw continued reliance on services, with co-creation, stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping, and small-scale real-life testing and experimentation being particularly essential. Notably, expert opinion and advisory services stood out as a consistently crucial resource, valued by all visiting researchers throughout the entirety of their TA projects, highlighting its pivotal role from project initiation to completion. This comprehensive utilization of services underscores the multifaceted support provided by the AUTH Health care transition Living Lab, ensuring the success of the TA research endeavors.

3.3 INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room

Between April and October 2023, INTRAS VR/AR environment and Snoezelen room successfully facilitated two distinctive Transnational Access (TA) projects, engaging a total of four researchers (out of five planned). These projects, namely ID13 (VirtuaLearn) and ID42 (IDENTIA), have significantly contributed to the exploration and advancement of Virtual Reality (VR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in health research, shaping the development of the IDENTIA system. Their focus ranged from motor learning in immersive environments to early detection of dementia, showcasing the diverse potential of VR/AR technologies to address complex health challenges. This period of collaboration fostered not only the development of innovative methodologies but also enhanced international collaboration and knowledge exchange. These projects, distinct in their focus yet unified in their utilization of immersive technologies, underscore the pivotal role of interdisciplinary cooperation and adaptability in contemporary research endeavors. From the TAs, ID13 took a fully remote format to accommodate researchers' requirements, while ID42 performed both remote and in-person. Once the ID42 researcher travelled from Argentina, the Living Lab in agreement with the VITALISE consortium covered the full costs of the transcontinental flights that surpassed the standard budget defined per researcher in this budget line, yet, in this case the in-person TA phase was critical for the researcher.

In particular, the “VirtuaLearn” project (ID13) aimed to explore the neural aspects of motor learning in immersive VR environments. To address the initial challenge of needing a dedicated software developer for Fitts Law Model development, the Living Lab Project shifted its focus towards understanding user experience, requirements, and usability challenges by studying the real-world implementation of an existing VR multisensory device. This approach allowed the project to gather insights that could guide future research investments and planning. By learning from the experiences of the team and stakeholders, the project management ensured that the project stayed viable and in harmony with the resources at hand. The transition to utilizing a Multisensorial VR system, instead of developing a new tool, exemplifies adaptability and resourcefulness in research. Key services utilized included: i. Expert Opinion and Advisory Services both for supporting the shift in research focus, and for providing insights from clinical and technical point of view into the VR application used for the project's objectives; ii. Access to Data (also include access to license) from previous studies involving the Multisensorial VR System allowed for a richer analysis and understanding of its impact, informing the research direction; iii. Concept and Proof-of-Concept Tests with initial testing with the VR app provided essential feedback for refining the research approach and confirming the requirements for the own developments the research team were planning; iv. Simulation Test & Usability Testing assessing the Multisensorial VR System usability and its potential from a

multidisciplinary point of view, contributing to the development of a comprehensive research protocol for the planned study. Researcher highlighted the value of the Living Lab's adaptability and support.

Moving to "IDENTIA" project (ID42), the focus was on developing a VR-based screening system for early dementia detection using AI. This project demonstrated the innovative application of VR and AI in medical research, with significant services from the LL including: i. Expert Opinion and Advisory Services offered crucial insights into the application of VR for cognitive assessments and the integration of machine learning techniques, emphasizing crucial elements and unique aspects of digital interventions; ii. Co-Creation Session enabled the researcher and project team involved to work closely with VR developers and clinicians providing insights and requirements for the design of a VR environment that accurately reflects cognitive tasks for early dementia detection; iii. Simulation Test providing a controlled setting to preliminarily assess the VR system's functionality and gather initial feedback on the model assessment capabilities; iv. Small-Scale Real-Life Testing and Experimentation with sessions conducted with professionals and older adults to pre-validate the system's usability and effectiveness in detecting early signs of dementia, providing valuable data for refining the system while also included Usability Testing evaluating how user-friendly and accessible the VR system was to the target demographic, incorporating feedback from actual users to enhance the system's design and functionality.

The collaborative experience highlighted the benefits of Living Labs as ecosystems for innovation, where researchers, developers, and end-users come together to co-create and test solutions in real-life contexts. The Living Lab's role in facilitating these connections, providing access to specialized equipment, and offering expert advisory services, was instrumental in the TA projects.

3.4 Thomas More Experience lab

Six applicants of two research groups applied to conduct research in this infrastructure. Unfortunately, one project with two researchers was cancelled in the preparation stage due to medical issues concerning the lead applicant. Consequently, only one project with four external visitors was conducted on this RI. The hosting Living Lab manages a large panel, but did not have any prior experience working with hearing impaired individuals. It was interesting for us to contact patient organisations and become aware of challenges and obstacles these individuals face in everyday life. An innovative technical solution such as the ChatterGlove could really improve communication between hearing impaired individuals and their environment. Although family and friends are often able to speak sign language, this is less common in a working environment. The exoskeleton and accompanying application enhance social interaction on the work floor and improve quality of life in hearing impaired individuals.

Services that were used from the Living Lab in project ID36 were Capacity building, Expert opinion and advisory services, Legal, regulation and safety standard support; Panel management; Intake and matching; Living lab project planning and management; co-creation session; Prototyping testing, small-scale real-life testing and experimentation; and Usability testing. The Living Lab helped submitting the ethical application at the local ethical committee, as the students in this project had little or no experience on this. Thomas More technical experts helped improving the prototype by 3D printed parts that made the ChatterGlove more comfortable to wear. Consequently, the prototype was tested in 13 hearing impaired individuals. As the researchers did not speak Dutch, LiCalab's panel manager recruited the participants by contacting patient organisations. She also moderated the usability testing sessions where hearing impaired individuals were accompanied by a friend or family member to facilitate communication. Participants signed the alphabet and numbers and went through some predefined scenarios concerning daily life issues. This standardised testing made it possible to compare data of different people and train the model to understand the Flemish dialect of sign language. A second part comprised free and spontaneous speech where hearing impaired individuals talked about their daily hassles, experience with speech technology and sign language and their experience with the ChatterGlove. The co-creation session with the technical experts was performed in English and facilitated by LiCalab's panel manager, who recruited the experts.

The topic of the study was very interesting and challenging for the LL team requiring to explore new horizons. The LL team learned about the daily hassles of hearing-impaired individuals when

contacting patient organisations and became aware of the struggles they are facing. However, communication with the research team was very difficult. Information and documents needed for ethical application were provided with delays, resulting in the need to postpone the planned visit. Many reminders were needed to fulfil administrative requirements such as signing the Contract Agreement or completing the requested feedback surveys or final report. The working attitude could be better for some of these students. This might be due to the lack of experience of the team consisting of one PhD candidate and 3 master students. Nevertheless, we could state that the study was successful, led to valuable insights and could have a large impact on the quality of life of hearing-impaired individuals in the long term.

3.5 UPM-LifeSTech- LifeSpace Living Lab

The Wait Safe patient queue management system and the LifeSpace Living Lab activities stand out as the first TA. The former, tested both in controlled and real-world environments, leveraged the LifeSpace Living Lab's services to enhance the well-being of patients and medical staff, and optimize scheduling. The TA activities encompassed training sessions, skill development, and feedback collection from different stakeholders, including healthcare professionals and hospital managers from the private sector so gathering advice from several experts. The solution was also tested in a hospital setting implementing a user recruitment strategy and development of user materials. These activities were crucial in equipping participants with the necessary expertise to conduct the TA. However, the attitude from the external research was questionable so impact the implementation of the activities according to the plan established.

Conversely, with ID59 LifeSpace were focus on Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADLs) which offered rich insights into the role of technology in enhancing aspects of daily life, such as transportation, communication, and home maintenance. Through a combination of training, task execution, and ethical discussions, external researchers gained a comprehensive understanding of smart technology's current adoption levels, barriers, and potential benefits. This was facilitated by innovative collaborative and creative tools such as Miro boards, which enabled documentation and reflective engagement, even with the added challenge of remote participation and language barriers.

4 Conclusion

This final comprehensive report presents an overview about the performed TA activities to four research infrastructures that participate in WP9 TA2, highlighting the significance of transnational access in facilitating collaborative research efforts across different research infrastructures. By granting researchers access to state-of-the-art Living Lab infrastructures, the project aims to foster innovation and advance knowledge in the field of transitional care, demonstrating the power of collaborative, interdisciplinary research.

This final report offers a snapshot of the collaborative efforts and achievements within WP9's TA2. It signifies the project's progress towards fostering innovation, knowledge exchange, and interdisciplinary research in the realm of transitional care. This report serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders, researchers, and policymakers, providing insights into the project's TA outcomes, illustrating the strides made in promoting innovation and facilitating knowledge exchange.

5 Annexes

Below we present the After TA Evaluation Questionnaire:

T3 AFTER TA EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE (MANDATORY)

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Disclaimer

The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

Dear researcher,

Thank you very much for participating in our Vitalise Transnational Access.

We highly appreciate you taking the time to reply to this mandatory questionnaire as it will help us continue improving the content of the Transnational Access for future participants. Completion of the questionnaire will take approximately 5-10 minutes.

The questionnaire is **not anonymous**. The next set of questions, comprising the sections Transnational Access, Living lab collaboration and Vitalise products, invite you to reflect on your journey and provide feedback on the Transnational Access.

Kind regards,

The Vitalise consortium

* Name of the researcher filling the questionnaire [Open question]

TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS

* 1. How likely are you to recommend the Transnational Access to your colleagues or other researchers (0 not at all – 10 very likely)?

Only values of at most 10 are allowed

* 2. How well were your expectations regarding the Transnational Access met?

- +2 TA output was much higher than expected
- +1 TA output was somewhat higher than expected
- 0 TA output was as expected
- 1 TA output was somewhat lower than expected
- 2 TA output was much lower than expected

* 3. How useful is the inclusion of a Fast Track Training program during Transnational Access? (0 not useful - 10 very useful)

Only values of at most 10 are allowed

* 4. What did you appreciate most about the Transnational Access? [Open question]

* 5. Do you have any suggestions for improvement concerning the Transnational Access? [Open question]

LIVING LAB COLLABORATION

6. Please rate the following services provided by the hosting Living Lab in terms of quality. If services are not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column. [partly open question]

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Understand end-user needs and problems	<input type="radio"/>					
* Methodological support and guidance	<input type="radio"/>					
* Selection/recruitment of test persons	<input type="radio"/>					
* Expertise/support with end users (co-creation, field test, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
* Physical infrastructure (research labs, tools, co-creation space, demo house, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					

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Other, namely ...

* 7A. Please select the research infrastructure(s) you have visited. Multiple answers are possible.

- LICALAB / LiCalab Older Adults Homes
- LICALAB / MOBILAB & Care – Motion lab
- LICALAB / Thomas More Experience lab
- AUTH / AUTH Living Environment simulation
- AUTH / AUTH Healthcare Transitions Living Lab
- AUTH / AUTH Centrifuge Rehabilitation Living Lab
- AIT / AIT Technology Experience Lab
- TREABAG / Nagykovácsi Wellbeing Living Lab
- GAIA / GAIA and Smart Spaces
- GAIA / GAIA Ozean Living Lab
- INTARS / INTRAS Rehabilitation Living Lab
- INTARS / INTRAS VR/AR Environment and Snoezelen Room
- INTARS / INTRAS Living Lab – MIND lab for AHA & Independent Living
- McGill / McGill-UDEM-CRIR Living Lab
- UPM / LifeSpace by UPM
- LAUREA / Laurea Simulated Hospital
- LAUREA / Laurea Activity Living Lab

* 7B. What do you think are key strengths in terms of expertise/coaching/etc. of [answer 7A]'s present research infrastructure from the perspective of your research or study? [Open question – this question should be presented for all RI selected]

* 7C. What weaknesses in [answer 7A]'s present research infrastructure do you believe need to be addressed? (These could include any aspect of the institution that hinders your research productivity). [Open question - this question should be presented for all RI selected]

VITALISE PRODUCTS

8. How often did you use any of the following Vitalise products during your Transnational Access?

	0 - Never	1 - Once	2- Several times	3 - Weekly	4 - Daily
* Data Tool	<input type="radio"/>				
* Panel Management tool	<input type="radio"/>				
* Vitalise website	<input type="radio"/>				
* Vitalise Wiki page	<input type="radio"/>				

9. Please rate the following products in terms of user friendliness. If a product was not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column.

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Data Tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Panel Management tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Vitalise website	<input type="radio"/>					
* Vitalise Wiki page	<input type="radio"/>					

10. Please rate the following products in terms of usefulness as it relates to your research process. If a product was not applicable to your study, please indicate this in the right column.

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Data Tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Panel Management tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Vitalise website	<input type="radio"/>					
* Vitalise Wiki page	<input type="radio"/>					

* **11. In what way did any of these products affect your Transnational Access work? (for example, saved me time, greater accuracy, etc.)**
[Open question]

12. How much do you anticipate needing the following services or products in your future work? (Very low probability – very high probability).

	-2 Very low	-1 Low	0 Neutral	+1 High	+2 Very high	NA
* Understand end-user needs and problems	<input type="radio"/>					
* Methodological support and guidance	<input type="radio"/>					
* Selection/recruitment of test persons	<input type="radio"/>					
* Expertise/support with end users (co-creation, field test, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
* Physical infrastructure (research labs, tools, co-creation space, demo house, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>					
* Data tool	<input type="radio"/>					
* Panel management tool	<input type="radio"/>					

13. Is there any other service or product you anticipate needing in your future research? [Open question]

14. Any additional comments you would like to share with us? [Open question]

Thank you very much!

Submit